

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

NON-ALIGNED MOVEMENT AND AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The article talks about the Non-Aligned Movement, which is one of the largest associations in the world, and the position of the Azerbaijan state in this association. The Non-Aligned Movement, which unites 120 member states, is a very serious and globally important cooperation platform, which is a participant of 10 internationally influential institutions such as the United Nations, the African Union, and the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, as well as 17 states with observer status. By the number of its members, the Non-Aligned Movement is the largest international organization in the world after the United Nations. For this reason, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, using such international platforms, which play an important role in determining world politics and realities, conveys the truths of Azerbaijan to the world and achieves the transformation of Azerbaijan into a place of international cooperation where global issues are discussed. In this way, the head of the country is gradually bringing our state closer to strategic goals and to the ranks of the leading states of the international community. In this way, the importance of the Non-Aligned Movement for Azerbaijan is explained in the article. The article also shows that the Non-Aligned Movement takes an unequivocal position on the issue of the territorial integrity of states, based on the basic principles of international law. Also, the article presents the support of the sovereign rights and territorial integrity of the Azerbaijan state, the unequivocal condemnation of any aggression against Azerbaijan, and the unequivocal support of the inviolability of its internationally recognized borders.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Non-Aligned Movement, conflict, politics, territorial integrity

Introduction. After regaining its independence, Azerbaijan tried to establish mutual relations with all members of the international community, and great success was achieved in this work. The political, economic and humanitarian relations established with the world's leading countries have led Azerbaijan to development in all fields and raised it to the ranks of the world's leading countries. With the restoration of its independence, the state of Azerbaijan, which has been pursuing a policy of representation in various international organizations, has started to establish mutual relations with the countries of the world since 1991. Having been elected as a member of the United Nations, the world's leading organization, since March 1992, Azerbaijan has actively participated in all events of this organization and has demonstrated its position in world politics. It has revealed its will as a state in humanitarian disasters, political crises, and global challenges.

The national leader Heydar Aliyev, who started leading the country since 1993, has also achieved important achievements in the transformation of Azerbaijan, which was ruled within the framework of imperial laws for seventy years, into a subject of the international world by using his many years of statehood policy. Continuing the successful foreign policy of the national leader Heydar Aliyev, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev also confidently protected the political interests of Azerbaijan in international organizations, proved that he is a head of state who is independent from the highest chairs and is not subject to any political influences. As a result of this, during the spread of the "Covid 19" virus, which took the world by storm in December 2019 and caused global crises in 2020, Azerbaijan was in the spotlight with its humanitarian support. Also, as a result of the

purposeful policy of President Ilham Aliyev, the restoration of our broken territorial integrity and the liberation of our occupied lands have been achieved by realizing the implementation of the decisions adopted by the UN Security Council but not implemented.

The article reflects the activities of the Azerbaijan state within the Non-Aligned Movement. Information is provided on ensuring that Azerbaijani citizens who have left their homes and lands and become refugees live in other regions of Azerbaijan. The fact that the state of Azerbaijan stands by the people of the world in the fight against the "Corona virus" pandemic, which has engulfed the world since 2019, is confirmed in the article.

Literature Review: Various studies have been conducted on the Non-Aligned Movement and Azerbaijan, the subject of the study. The scientific works of the researchers were cited. When conducting research on the subject, recent press examples were referred to. As a source, the articles in the official state press agencies "Yeni Azerbaijan newspaper", "Respublika newspaper", "Khalq newspaper", and "Azerbaijan" newspaper have been analyzed. Also from the official websites: <https://president.az>, <https://mfa.gov.by/multilateral/organization>, <https://modern.az/aktual>, <https://respublika-news.az/>, <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/dvizhenie-nepriosoedineniya-vazhnyy-faktor-mirovoy-politiki-vtoroy-poloviny-hh-Sited-like-veka-were-used-and-comparisons-were-made>.

Materials and methods: The polarization that took place in the world during the cold war years after the Second World War reminded the political arena leading to a new bloody war. The states suffering from the war, which built their economies for the sake of the

welfare of their people, began to act against the interests of the imperialist forces by pursuing a policy against the creation of any military blocs and armaments. These states founded the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM) in order not to be drawn into the conflict between the two political-military poles. The foreign policy and diplomatic activity of the states that declared their independence in Asia and Africa began to take a special place in international relations. In 1947, in Delhi, the central city of India, which stood out among the states fighting for independence, at a non-governmental meeting between Asian countries, Indian Prime Minister J. Nehru called on Asian countries to cooperate, emphasized the importance of coming together for the abolition of the colonial administration policy and the development of the national economy. However, disagreements became the main obstacle on the way to achieving this goal, and they could not agree on the coordination of the struggle for independence (2, p. 255).

The events that took place in the world, the geostrategy that emerged after the Second World War gave the victorious states the opportunity to successfully implement their future plans. As is known, at that time there were blocks of Eastern-socialist and Western-capitalist states. Both blocs were secretly and openly fighting each other for influence all over the world. Of course, the object of that struggle was the newly independent states. In order not to fall into the "rodent ambush" of the world giants, the states that gained independence also tried not to fall into the "trap" in the newly created conditions. This could only be achieved by coming together, organizing conferences, making proposals to be accepted in the political arena, and making deliberate decisions against the inevitable threat. The newly independent states planned to establish their economies by establishing mutual cooperation with them, not to fall under the political and economic dependence of both the western capitalist world and the eastern socialist, communist states. The point was that the socialist front wanted to use the young, independent states against the western capitalist world. Transnational companies and international agreements played a special role in this case. The newly created independent states naturally could not maintain their economic independence individually. For this, it was necessary to unite in certain blocks.

Members of the Non-Aligned Movement skillfully exploited the West-East conflict when entering the international arena. Although the movement changed its priorities during its existence, it did not change its goals. The members of the movement first asked for unilateral concessions from the big powers (blocs) for their members at the subregional and regional level, and then at the global level. The Non-Aligned Movement defined priorities for its development in the 21st century (14).

Indonesia took the main step in this direction. In 1955, Indonesia acted as one of the initiators of convening a conference with the participation of 29 Asian and African countries in one of its cities, Bandung. The Bandung conference became a new event in international politics in the period after World War II (5, p. 193).

In 1961, the countries freed from the colonial policy began to create various organizations to participate more actively in international relations. As you can see, the emergence of the non-alignment movement was related to the initiative of the liberated countries. Prime Minister of India J. Nehru, President of Egypt J. Nasir, President of Yugoslavia I. Tito, President of Indonesia A. Suharto played a major role in the organization of this movement. At the conference held in Belgrade in September 1961, the leaders of 25 countries discussed the issue of non-alignment and approved the principles of the non-alignment movement. In these principles, it was determined that the countries joining the movement should live independently, implement a peaceful policy, not join any military alliance, and not place military bases of foreign countries in their territories. At the Second Conference of the Non-Aligned Movement held in Cairo in 1964, representatives of 46 countries and representatives of 63 countries took part in the III Conference held in Lusaka in 1970, demonstrated the line of coordinating their foreign policies, and declared to the world that they were in the same position on important issues of international life (2, p. 276).

Considering that in the 60s of the 20th century, the members of the movement came together at the Cairo conference (1964) against the pressure of the countries that wanted to destroy the Non-Aligned Movement, and the Non-Aligned Movement was finally formed and strengthened at the Lusaka conference (15).

Currently, this organization, which consists of one hundred and twenty members, has become one of the important multilateral mechanisms involved in the system of international relations. As mentioned, the goal of the organization is to help peace, security and development in the world based on international legal norms. One of the main principles of the organization and operation of the Non-Aligned Movement is that it serves as a forum for cooperation among the states of the union. As mentioned above, the Non-Aligned Movement currently has 120 members, 18 observer states and 10 observer international organizations.

Faced with the military intervention of Armenia, which has been making territorial claims against our lands since 1988, the state of Azerbaijan, in the 90s of the 20th century, literally fought for the protection of the regained independence in world politics. The national leader of the Azerbaijani people, Heydar Aliyev, tried to promote the occupying policy of Armenia together with the patrons of the world by conveying the fair position of Azerbaijan to the world leaders at all levels. Ilham Aliyev, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, who took over the leadership of Azerbaijan in 2003, continued Heydar Aliyev's political line and paid attention to the implementation of the resolutions adopted by the UN Security Council regarding the occupied lands of Azerbaijan. In this matter, he tried to gain the support of the world's main political organizations and demonstrate political will in recognizing Armenia as an occupying state. Obtaining the special support of the "Non-Aligned Movement" mentioned in the study, becoming a member of the organization, and participating in its events have been one of the main directions of the political line of the President of Azerbaijan.

The Republic of Azerbaijan initially participated in the Non-Aligned Movement as an observer, and in January 2011 applied to become a member of the organization in accordance with the procedural rules. On March 16, 2011, at the meeting of the Coordination Bureau of the Non-Aligned Movement held in New York, the issue of Azerbaijan's membership in the movement was discussed, and on May 26, 2011, Azerbaijan was accepted as a full member of the Non-Aligned Movement in Bali, Indonesia, with the unanimous support of the member states of the organization (1).

According to the official document adopted at the meeting of the Coordinating Bureau of the Non-Aligned Movement in the city of Sharm el-Sheikh, Arab Republic of Egypt on May 9-12, 2012, the Armenia-Azerbaijan Nagorno-Karabakh conflict is based on respect for the territorial integrity of both states, non-use of force against each other and in the international world. expressed support for the settlement based on the principles of the inviolability of recognized borders. In the Final Document of the Non-Aligned Movement, which was adopted at the 16th Summit of Heads of State and Government, held in Tehran, Islamic Republic of Iran, on August 30-31, 2012, the states expressed their support for the resolution of the conflict "within the territorial integrity, sovereignty and internationally recognized borders" of the Republic of Azerbaijan. (8).

On May 28-29, 2014, the next, XVII ministerial meeting of the Non-Aligned Movement was held in Algeria, one of the main victims of the colonial policy. In the final document of the meeting of the member states of the Non-Aligned Movement, the call for the resolution of the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict within the framework of UN Security Council resolutions 822, 853, 874, 884 and the territorial integrity, sovereignty and internationally recognized borders of the Republic of Azerbaijan showed that the international community supports the fair position of Azerbaijan(2). The fact that the Non-Aligned Movement is an organization against unfairness and injustice in the world, and the support of the political will of the Azerbaijan state within this organization, and the fact that this organization took a stand against the pressures of major powers, showed that the organization has become a leading organization at the international level. The summit meetings and conferences of the Non-Aligned Movement, which has become a place for discussion of issues that need to be solved at the global level, which is expanding more and more, contributed to the diplomatic negotiations held to ensure the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan and the unconditional return of the occupied Azerbaijani territories. In the summit meetings held in 2018 and 2019, the member countries of the Non-Aligned Movement supported Azerbaijan's rightful position based on international law. At the Summit of the Non-Aligned Movement held in Baku in 2019, the Chairmanship of the Movement for 2019-2022 was transferred to the Republic of Azerbaijan. After Uganda, which will be the next chairman of the Movement, expressed that it could take over the chairmanship 1 year later, the member states of the Non-Aligned Movement applied for Azerbaijan's chairmanship of the Movement for an addi-

tional 1 year, taking into account the successful chairmanship of the Movement, and the Azerbaijani side expressed its loyalty to the accepted principles and values of the Movement taking into account, gave a positive response to the application. Thus, Azerbaijan's chairmanship of the Non-Aligned Movement was extended until 2023 (8).

On April 4, 2020, the Coordinating Bureau of the Non-Aligned Movement adopted the "Communique on the so-called "elections" held in the occupied territories of the Republic of Azerbaijan". The Non-Aligned Movement, which is the second largest political platform after the UN and unites 120 countries, as well as numerous other organizations and states, once again clearly demonstrated that the entire world community rejects the occupation policy of the Republic of Armenia and its consequences. It was declared that they do not recognize the so-called "presidential and parliamentary elections" held in the occupied Nagorno-Karabakh region of the Republic of Azerbaijan on March 31, 2020, and consider this act illegal (4).

A summit in the format of the Contact Group of the Non-Aligned Movement took place soon after. The appeal of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev to the UN Secretary General on convening a special session of the UN General Assembly dedicated to COVID-19 on behalf of the member states in the capacity of the chairman of the Non-Aligned Movement was supported by more than 130 countries. The state of Azerbaijan allocated financial aid to some international organizations and foreign countries in order to fight against the pandemic (6, p. 216).

On May 4, 2020, on the initiative of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, a video conference of the Contact Group on the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic was organized in the format of the Summit of the Non-Aligned Movement on the topic "We are together against COVID-19". The Working Group on the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic of the movement was established. The group was tasked with preparing a single database that would reflect the main medical, social and humanitarian needs of the member states in the fight against the "Corona virus" pandemic. At that meeting, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, as the chairman of the Non-Aligned Movement, took the initiative to convene a special session of the UN General Assembly dedicated to the fight against COVID-19.

The UN Secretary General announced the convening of a special session on July 10, 2020. On December 3, 2020, a special session of the UN General Assembly was organized in connection with the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, and at the opening of that session, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev spoke as the chairman of the Non-Aligned Movement and the initiator of this special session. In the session, the heads of state and government, who talked about the catastrophes of the pandemic and the crisis situation created for the world, expressed their gratitude to Azerbaijan and the country's leadership, who initiated the session (7).

The members of the Non-Aligned Movement conveyed Azerbaijan's rightful voice to the members of the

international community even when large-scale offensive operations against Azerbaijan began on September 27, 2020. At the session of the UN General Assembly held on October 9, 2020, a Special Declaration condemning Armenia's aggression was adopted. In the declaration, the member states of the Movement expressed their solidarity with Azerbaijan by demonstrating a principled position.

As it is known, the Non-Aligned Movement, in which Azerbaijan plays a leading role, has an important role in protecting the rights of oppressed countries in the world and preventing humanitarian crises at the global level. The Non-Aligned Movement, which is a member of the states that have come together to establish peace at the global level, has become one of the main means for Azerbaijan to have a say in the international arena. The business visits of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev to the states that are members of the Non-Aligned Movement, the diplomatic relations of these states with Azerbaijan, mutual cooperation in both political, social and humanitarian spheres show that there are close ties between Azerbaijan and the Non-Aligned Movement.

Discussion: Acting as a protector of peace and security in the world, the Non-Aligned Movement opposes all aggressions and wars in any region of the world with the countries it has joined. Within the framework of the Non-Aligned Movement, Azerbaijan carried out work towards the return of its territories that had been occupied for more than 30 years. The state of Azerbaijan, which contributed to the solution of global problems in the world within the Non-Aligned Movement, proposed that all states come together during the pandemic and provide financial assistance to poor countries. Azerbaijan was one of the initiators of holding meetings of the United Nations Organization related to the world's global problems.

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